

MECHANICAL PERFORMANCE AND FRACTURE CHARACTERISTIC OF BAMBOO FIBER REINFORCED POLYETHYLENE BIOCOMPOSITES PREPARED BY ROTATIONAL MOLDING

Supaphorn Thumsorn^{*1,3}, Jitlada Boonlertsamut¹, Thanadol Petchnoi¹, Saowaluk Boonmawieng¹,
Narongchai O-Charoen², Hiroyuki Hamada³

¹Department of Textile Engineering, Rajamangala University of Technology Thanyaburi
39 Moo. 1, Klong 6, Thanyaburi, Pathumthani, 12110 Thailand
Email: supaphorn.t@rmutt.ac.th, web page: <http://www.engineer.rmutt.ac.th/>

²Department of Materials Engineering, Rajamangala University of Technology Thanyaburi
39 Moo. 1, Klong 6, Thanyaburi, Pathumthani, 12110 Thailand
Email: narongchai.o@en.rmutt.ac.th, web page: <http://www.engineer.rmutt.ac.th/>

³Department of Advanced Fibro-Science, Kyoto Institute of Technology
Matsugasaki, Kyoto, 606-8585 Japan
Email: hhamada@kit.ac.jp, web page: <http://www.kit.ac.jp/>

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ABSTRACT

The composites of linear low density polyethylene (LLDPE) reinforced with bamboo fiber were prepared in this study. Maleic anhydride grafted polyethylene (MA-g-PE) was used as a coupling agent between bamboo fiber and the LLDPE matrix. The size of bamboo fiber was screened by 325 mesh size. The contents of bamboo fibers were varied from 0-20 weight percent (wt%) of LLDPE. The amount of LLDPE-g-MA was 2 wt%. LLDPE, bamboo fiber and MA-g-PE were ground into powder before fabricating to the composites by rotational molding. The effect of bamboo fiber contents on morphology, thermal properties and mechanical performance of the composites was investigated. The incorporation of bamboo fiber increased tensile modulus, hardness and crystallinity of the LLDPE/BF composites. On the other hand, tensile strength, elongation at break and fracture toughness of the composites decreased with increasing BF contents. It can be noted that LLDPE-g-MA improved adhesion between bamboo fiber and LLDPE matrix. However, the interfacial strength of the composites would be enhanced in order to overcome the fracture toughness of the LLDPE/bamboo fiber composites.

1 INTRODUCTION

Polymer composites are significantly used in the present day due to their light weight and high specific strength. Natural fiber reinforced composites are classified as an environmentally friendly composites and green products [1-2]. Various kinds of natural fibers are used for reinforcing i.e. flax fiber, jute fiber, sisal fiber, kenaf fiber, banana fiber and bamboo fiber [3-7]. These natural fibers from renewable resources are continuous researched according to the environmental concerns. Okubo et al [6] showed the development of bamboo-based polymer composites. The chemical composition of bamboo fiber consists of cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin, which needs to removal lignin from the fiber in order to obtain higher mechanical performance of the bamboo reinforced polymer composites [6-7].

There are various processes for preparing the polymer composites such as injection molding, hand lay-up, compression molding and rotational molding. In this research focused on using rotational molding for the composites preparation. Rotational molding technique [8-10] can be fabricated a hollow products, which no stress concentrator in the products. Torres and Aragon [10] researched on the product of natural fiber using sisal fiber and cabuya fiber reinforced polyethylene by rotational

molding. The incorporation of natural fiber led the matrix becomes more brittle and the ability of the materials to absorb impact energy decreases with regardless on the fiber used.

The aim of this research was to develop bamboo fiber reinforced polyethylene composites with fabricated by rotational molding. The rotational molding machine was established by our Department. The effect of bamboo fiber contents on mechanical performance, fracture toughness, morphology and thermal properties of the composites was elucidated.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

Linear low density polyethylene (LLDPE), Innoplus Grade LL9640UP, was supplied by PTT Global Public Co., Ltd., Thailand. The melt flow index (MFI) of LLDPE was 4 g/10 min. Bamboo fiber (BF) was ground then sieved by standard sieving mesh no. 326 with an average particle size of 35 μm . LLDPE grafted maleic anhydride (LLDPE-g-MA), Fusabond® Grade EMB226DY, was supplied by Dupont. MFI of LLDPE-g-MA was 1.5 g/10 min.

Bamboo fiber contents were varied from 0, 5, 10, 15 and 20 percent by weight (wt%). LLDPE-g-MA was used as coupling agent between LLDPE matrix and reinforced bamboo fiber. The content of LLDPE-g-MA was used at 2 wt% of LLDPE matrix. Table 1 summarized the composition of materials used in this research.

2.2 Sample preparation

All materials were ground into powder before molding by a shuttle style rotational molding. This machine was developed by Department of Materials Technology, Rajamangala University of Technology Thanyaburi, Thailand. The sample was fabricated using a rectangular molded. The materials were placed in the molded and installed in the rotational molding machine. Temperature was set at 240 °C. The molded was heated for 10 min after that rotated to the cooling stage for 30 min before ejected.

2.3 Characterization

Tensile testing was carried out by universal testing machine (LLOYD, LR10K) according to ASTM D638. The gauge length was set at 50 mm. The testing speed was 10 mm/min.

Single-edge notched bending (SENB) test [11-13] was done by Instron universal testing machine (Instron 4206) according to ASTM D5045. The specimen was cut to the dimension of 60 mm long \times 10 mm wide \times 3 mm thickness with 2 mm notched depth. The span length was set at 48 mm at testing speed of 3 mm/min. Figure 1 shows schematic of SENB test.

Figure 1: Schematic of single notch edge bending test.

Fracture toughness was calculated by the following equations

$$K_Q = \left(\frac{P_Q}{BW^{1/2}} \right) f(x) \quad (1)$$

$$B, a, (w-a) > 2.5(K_Q / \sigma_y)^2 \quad (2)$$

Where: K_Q = Trial K_{IC} value ($\text{MPa} \cdot \text{m}^{1/2}$)
 P_Q = P_{max} = Maximum load (kN)
 B = Specimen thickness (mm)
 W = Specimen depth (mm)
 $f(x)$ = calculation function of K_Q

Where: K_Q = Trial K_{IC} value ($\text{MPa} \cdot \text{m}^{1/2}$)
 σ_y = the yield stress of the maximum load in a uniaxial tensile test (MPa)

Hardness of the specimen was test using hardness durometer (Shore D) by ASTM D785.

Morphology of tensile fractured surface and SEBN tested specimens were characterized by scanning electron microscope (SEM) (JEOL, JSM6510) and optical microscope, respectively.

Thermal properties were analyzed using differential scanning calorimeter (DSC, NETZSCH DSC200F). The test temperature was set at 30 to 200 C at heating and cooling rate of 10 C/min. The crystallinity of LLDPE was was calculated from the following equation.

$$\% X_c = \frac{\Delta H_f \times 100}{\Delta H_{f100}} \times \frac{1}{W_p} \quad (3)$$

Where X_c = Degree of crystallinity
 W_p = Weight fraction of polymer
 ΔH_f = Heat of fusion of polymer
 ΔH_{f100} = Heat of fusion of 100% PE Crystallization = 293 J/g [14]

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Mechanical properties

Figure 1 presents typical stress-strain curves of neat LLDPE and LLDPE/BF composite. The curves show large elongated of LLDPE while bamboo fiber inside the composites restrict their elongation. These results can be indicated ductile and tough characteristic of LLDPE whereas LLDPE/BF composites were brittle with high stiffness.

Figure 2: Stress-strain curves of neat LLDPE and LLDPE/bamboo fiber composites.

Table 1 tabulates tensile properties and hardness of LLDPE and the composites. Tensile strength and elongation at break of the composites decreased with adding bamboo fiber. It was considered that bamboo fiber presented as stress concentrators, which restricted elongation and tensile load transferring in the composites. Tensile modulus and hardness of the composites increased with increasing bamboo fiber contents. It was attributed to the stiffness of the bamboo fiber and the good adhesion between bamboo fiber and the LLDPE matrix when using LLDPE-g-MA as the coupling agent.

Bamboo fiber content (wt%)	Tensile modulus (GPa)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Elongation at break (%)	Hardness (Shore D)
0	0.03±0.01	9.10±0.28	-	50.6 ±.65
5	0.54±0.06	9.91±0.57	12.05±1.04	44.0±.15
10	0.48± 0.15	6.59±0.11	7.85±0.58	46.8±1.14
15	0.82±0.11	8.76±0.41	6.15±0.38	47.2±1.23
20	0.94±0.04	8.86±0.36	5.17±0.14	52.7±2.06

Table 1: Tensile properties of LLDPE and LLDPE/bamboo fiber composites.

3.2 Fracture toughness

Fracture toughness of the composites of LLDPE reinforced with bamboo fiber was elucidated using single notch bending test of 2 mm V-notch specimens. Figure 3 illustrates the effect of bamboo fiber on fracture toughness, K_{IC} , of neat LLDPE and the composites. It can be seen that fracture toughness of the composites decreased with increasing bamboo fiber contents. It can be indicated that bamboo fiber cannot overcome to improve fracture characteristic of the LLDPE/BF composites. The fracture resistance of the composites might be decreased due to increasing stress concentration point by BF and less energy absorption as well as low interfacial adhesion between fiber and the matrix in the composites [10, 12].

Figure 3: Effect of BF contents on fracture toughness of the composites.

3.3 Morphology observation

Figure 4 presents SEM photographs of cryogenic fractured surface of neat LLDPE and the composites at various BF contents. SEM photographs showed ductile fracture characteristic of LLDPE as shown in Figure 1 (a) while LLDPE/BF composites were brittle as presented in Figure 1 (b)-(e). SEM results of the composites indicated that the adhesion between of bamboo fiber and the LLDPE

matrix was improved by using LLDPE-g-MA as the coupling agent in the composites. However, at low magnification, large void contents were presented in the composites, which might be related to water absorption of bamboo fiber during rotational molding.

Figure 5 shows optical photographs of neat LLDPE and the composites after SENB testing. The results confirmed that the composites were delamination and faster crack propagation when increasing bamboo fiber contents as presented in Figure 5 (b)-(e). Therefore, void contents and stress concentrator of bamboo fiber affected on the declination of tensile strength, elongation and fracture toughness of the LLDPE/BF composites [10].

Figure 4: SEM photographs of neat LLDPE and LLDPE/bamboo fiber composites.

Figure 5: Optical photographs of neat LLDPE and LLDPE/bamboo fiber composites.

3.4 Thermal properties

DSC thermograms of neat LLDPE and the composites are shown in Figures 6-7. Thermal properties of these composites are summarized in Table 2. Endothermic and exothermic thermograms of neat LLDPE and the composites were similar. Melting temperature (T_m) and crystallization temperature (T_c) of LLDPE slightly decreased when increasing bamboo fiber contents. It was attributed to smaller of crystal size in the composites as compared to in neat LLDPE. Therefore, bamboo fiber can be acted as nucleating agent for LLDPE crystallization in the composites. The incorporation of bamboo fiber increased crystallinity of LLDPE in the composites due to the heterogeneous nucleating effect of bamboo fiber. It can be noted that crystallinity of the LLDPE/BF composites would enhancing tensile modulus and hardness of the composites.

Figure 6: Endothermic DSC thermograms of neat LLDPE and LLDPE/bamboo fiber composites.

Figure 7: Exothermic DSC thermograms of neat LLDPE and LLDPE/bamboo fiber composites.

Bamboo fiber content (wt%)	T _m (°C) (Peak)	T _c (°C) (Peak)	Heat of fusion (J/g)	Crystallinity (%)
0	133.2	110.4	130.0	44.37
5	131.7	109.9	131.0	47.06
10	131.9	110.4	126.0	47.78
15	132.8	109.7	117.7	47.26
20	132.7	109.6	107.2	45.73

Table 2: Thermal properties of LLDPE and the LLDPE/bamboo fiber composites.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Biocomposites of LLDPE/bamboo fiber were made by rotational molding technique. Hollow products are easily fabricated from this molding technique. From the results, void contents and stress concentrator of bamboo fiber affected on the declination of tensile strength, elongation and fracture toughness of the LLDPE/BF composites. The incorporation of bamboo fiber increased crystallinity of LLDPE in the composites due to the heterogeneous nucleating effect of bamboo fiber. Tensile modulus and hardness of the composites increased with increasing bamboo fiber contents. It was attributed to the stiffness of the bamboo fiber and the good adhesion between bamboo fiber and the matrix as well as the enhancing of the composites crystallinity.

REFERENCES

- [1] K.G. Satyanarayana, G.G.C. Arizaga and F. Wypych, Biodegradable composites based on lignocellulosic fibers—An overview, *Progress in Polymer Science*, **34** 2009, pp. 982–1021 (doi:10.1016/j.progpolymsci.2008.12.002).
- [2] L. Yu and K.D. Lin Li, Polymer blends and composites from renewable resources, *Progress in Polymer Science*, **31**, 2006, pp. 576–602 (doi:10.1016/j.progpolymsci.2006.03.002).
- [3] S.K. Garkhail, R. W. H. Heijenrath and T. Peijs, Mechanical Properties of Natural-Fibre-Mat-Reinforced Thermoplastics based on Flax Fibres and Polypropylene, *Applied Composite Materials*, **7**, 2000, pp. 351–372 (DOI: 10.1023/A:1026590124038).
- [4] J. George, M.S. Sreekala and S. Thomas, A Review on Interface Modification and Characterization of Natural Fiber Reinforced Plastic Composites, *Polymer Engineering and Science*, **41**, 2001, pp. 1471-1485 (DOI: 10.1002/pen.10846).
- [5] G.N. Farahani, I. Ahmad and Z. Mosadeghzad, Effect of Fiber Content, Fiber Length and Alkali Treatment on Properties of Kenaf Fiber/UPR Composites Based on Recycled PET Wastes, *Polymer-Plastics Technology and Engineering*, **51**, 2012, pp. 634–639 (DOI: 10.1080/03602559.2012.659314).
- [6] K. Okubo, T. Fujii and Y. Yamamoto, Development of bamboo-based polymer composites and their mechanical properties, *Composites: Part A*, **35**, 2004, pp. 377–383 (doi:10.1016/j.compositesa.2003.09.017).
- [7] H.P.S. Abdul Khalil, I.U.H. Bhat, M. Jawaid, A. Zaidon, D. Hermawan and Y.S. Hadi, Bamboo fibre reinforced biocomposites: A review, *Materials and Design*, **42**, 2012, pp. 353-368 (doi: 10.1016/j.matdes.2012.06.015).
- [8] S. Liu and K.-H. Fu, Effect of enhancing fins on the heating/cooling efficiency of rotational molding and the molded product qualities, *Polymer Testing*, **27**, 2008, pp. 209–220 (doi:10.1016/j.polymertesting.2007.10.004).
- [9] M.C. Crameza, M.J. Oliveiraa and R.J. Crawford, Optimisation of rotational moulding of polyethylene by predicting antioxidant consumption, *Polymer Degradation and Stability*, **75**, 2002, pp. 321–327 (doi:10.1016/S0141-3910(01)00234-8).

- [10] F.G. Torres , C.L. Aragon, Final product testing of rotational moulded natural fibre-reinforced polyethylene, *Polymer Testing*, **25**, 2006, pp. 568–577 (doi:10.1016/j.polymeresting.2006.03.010).
- [11] J. Wu, Y.-W. Mai and B. Cotterell, Fracture toughness and fracture mechanisms of PBT/PC/IM blend Part I *Fracture Properties*, *Journal of Materials Science*, **28**, 1993, pp. 3373-3384.
- [12] M.K. Mahmoud, Fracture Toughness of Single-Edge Notched Fiber Reinforced Composite, *Polymer-Plastics Technology and Engineering*, **42**, 2003, pp. 659-676 (DOI: 10.1081=PPT-120023101).
- [13] J.O. Agunsoyea and V.S. Aigbodion, Bagasse filled recycled polyethylene bio-composites: Morphological and mechanical properties study, *Results in Physics*, **3**, 2013, pp. 187-194 (doi:10.1016/j.rinp.2013.09.003).
- [14] A. Turi, edited, *Thermal Characterization for Polymeric Materials*, Marcel Dekker, New York, 1999.